

Research On Modern And Contemporary Chinese Ancient Poetry And Art Songs From The Perspective Of Music Sociology

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: December 27, 2022</p> <p>Accepted: March 28, 2023</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Contemporary ,Chinese, Ancient Poetry,Art Song</p> <hr/> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7778852</p>	<p><i>Modern and contemporary Chinese ancient poetry art songs: especially refers to the artistic songs created since the 20th century. The definition of modern and contemporary music is taken from the stage reference of the development of Chinese new music, and divides the starting point of the development of modern and contemporary Chinese ancient poetry and art songs according to the modern and contemporary time points of Chinese music. Mainly from the aspects of language style and music form show uniqueness, at the same time on the basis of the fusion of thousands of years of Chinese national culture precipitation and European music creation technique, the ancient Chinese poetry and western art songs in the lyrics of the perfect fusion, become the modern and contemporary ancient poetry art song inheritance indispensable carrier. Because of the inherent form of ancient poetry and modern composition techniques, the author combines the cultural precipitation of the Chinese nation for thousands of years, and has the typical characteristics of the embryonic period of modern and contemporary ancient poetry and art songs, which will be the beginning of the study of this paper.</i></p>

Introduction

According to the big data analysis and search of the National Library of China, CNKI, Superstar, xiu and other platforms, a total of 23 works and 225 academic papers have been obtained. The authors collected and analyzed the data around the research related to this paper and according to the differences in the research subjects and content. This paper analyzes the development of modern and contemporary ancient poetry and art song under the background of music sociology. The following is a preliminary statistics and analysis of the relevant papers and journals on the modern and contemporary ancient poems and art songs and their research status in 20 years from 1991 to 2021, and on the development history and singing forms of ancient poems and songs.

Research Related To Music Sociology

The study of music sociology integrates the relationship between music and society abroad, which has been further developed in the historical development of China in the past hundred years. At present, the mature theoretical construction of music sociology includes Max Weber, Adorno, Siberman of Germany, Sohar of the former Soviet Union, as well as the ideological integration of Luo kai and Zeng Suijin on Chinese music society, which has a profound influence on the academic circle. In 1921, Max Weber (Max Webb), the world's first sociological study of music education, the Foundation of philosophical Reason and the Foundation of Socialism in Music Education, pointed out that " All primitive music education has the purpose of social culture."Sohar, a Soviet expert, summarized the theoretical practice of western music sociology in 1975 (formerly socialism and music culture), and comprehensively discussed the specific theoretical basis of music sociology. In 1981, Luo Zhuan published a paper entitled "Sociology of Music" in art research, which summed up some tendencies of music sociology: 1. He advocated that there are special code words and social character in music works. Understand the social code of this music by combining art criticism and cultural evaluation.2. The focus is to analyze the structure, characteristics, activities of human society —— sound community, and the relationship between social media and sound in the literary field.3. Try to seek the meaning of socialization in the iconic image of musical art. Throughout the subject content of the research and the important foreign research achievements on music sociology are mainly developed from the following aspects:

Discipline understanding of music sociology

Music sociology is a kind of knowledge to explore, identify and master the whole movement process and movement regularity of musical works in human social life. The name is understood from the meaning of musical sociology. This knowledge is closely related to both the two fields of music education and social life, which contains two categories: music education and social life. Then it reflects the mutual goal-oriented and

inseparable relationship between the two people in social life. There is no mutual exclusion between the composition, connotation and function, but there is no way to compare a certain musical reality with other musical reality, because they are also organically combined with each other: the structure of sociology is implied in the function of music, to establish the structure of sociology must change its connotation.

The Research Object Of Music Sociology

Since the era of the 20th century, music sociology has been formed as a special discipline, and our country also at the beginning of the 20th 80 century began to rise, explore and learn Chinese music socialism this unique course, so, in our country, music sociology has always been as a young professional field in the continuous vigorous development. However, it is undeniable that in the sense of academic and exploration, the more mature the professional development, the greater the value. A deeper thinking on the development of Chinese music sociology can be divided into three eras: the exploration stage (1980s to early 990 s), internalized absorption and development (1990 s); and the era of diversified development (early 21st century). The social functions produced by music works, the history of music development and the influence and behavior of music works in the economy and society all belong to the scope of the specific research of music sociology, which is also a movement of socialization of music works. At the same time, the social music and social activities are also composed of three modes of movement. Generally, people can vividly call these three aspects of social activities collectively as the vertical social movement of music, the horizontal social activities of music, and the comprehensive activities of music. The vertical social activities discussed in the paper mean that modern and contemporary ancient poetry art songs can be integrated in socialization in the promotion of historical development. The artistic characteristics have the remarkable characteristics of time and region, and have a corresponding connection with the horizontal activities of The Times. The so-called horizontal connection is the stage of social activity in the longitudinal operation of the music in any stage at the same time. This kind of whole social comprehensive activity runs through the horizontal and vertical, is another social activity of modern and contemporary ancient poetry art songs. Based on the horizontal activity characteristics of the music, we can further understand the vertical activity characteristics of the music, and finally produce the overall artistic activity. Another necessary condition for putting music into social movement is that musical activities are in the process of entering the society or have already existed in the society, that is, our thoughts and behaviors are also an important motivation for putting musical activities into social life.

Domestic music sociology research

In his book, *The Sociology of Music*, Sohar believes that the goal of music sociology is to enable people to use art and make it to obtain the greatest social benefits. Therefore, because people need art, they must use art reasonably and in the same destination, so the society is inseparable from music sociology. In recent years, there are also many investigative and research projects in the field of music sociology in China. For example, the study of Chinese folk songs started in the mid-1950s, and the study of ethnic and social history organized by the State Ethnic Affairs Commission of China after 1958, also include many investigations and studies related to the field of music sociology. People also began to investigate and study the historical characteristics of the development and the national and social composition of Chinese light music. In the early 1980s, the sociological study of music education was regarded as an independent discipline to study it in depth and introduce foreigners. Among the researchers at home and abroad, the scholars who mainly translated jin Jingyan and Zeng Sui-jin are devoted to the in-depth study of the sociology of music education. The former works include *Brief Research and Development of Chinese and Foreign Sociology of Music Education*, *Brief study of Chinese scholars on song literature*, Zeng Suijin and master, graduate students, Zeng Suijin include song literature course, song literature, its team research results, mainly involving the role of Chinese songs in the perspective of modern sociology and cultural transmission analysis.

Table 1 General Research Overview Of Chinese And Foreign Data In Music Sociology

The development node of the discipline	representative personage	nationality		representative work		research contents
1921	Max Webb		Germany	The Rational Foundation of Music "And the foundation of sociology."		The origin and evolution of the harmony system of modern European music and the band system are the symbol

						of the formal establishment of music sociology
After the 1930s	Westerman and Engel		German	"An Introduction to the Sociology of Music," "The Principles of the Sociology of Music."		Specific research on the social music life, the production and consumption of music commodities
1955	Kurt Blaukopf (K. Blaukopf)		Austria	"A Musical Life in Social Change."	Inheriting Weber, taking musical behavior as a social behavior to explain and explore the social causes of this behavioral process and the historical and realistic evolution of the whole musical practice	
	Böhme (K. Boehmer)		Germany	"The Sociology of Music."	The sociology of music is the study of the interaction between "music and society"	
1985	Sohar		the Soviet Union	"The Sociology of Music."	The object of the sociology of music is "social music life, that is, the process in which music culture plays its actual function under specific historical conditions. An in-depth analysis of the music culture"	
1977	Sheffield and Smeire		Britain	Whose Music — The Language of Music	The two books look with the same critical light	

				Sociology" Music —— Society —— Education	on the characteristics of the social system and the musical art,	
The 1980s	Lepelt (R. Leppert) and Susan McLarie (S.McClary)		Britain	The Music and Society	In fact, the subject of music research forms has become less and less, and the research forms composed of criticism and cultural musicology have gradually been replaced by the study of marginal disciplines	
The 1990s	Taylor Cowan		America	In Praise of Commercial Culture	Discuss the pop music culture market	
The 1980s	Once upon a time		China	An Introduction to the Sociology of Music: A Course of Music Sociology	He is committed to the discipline construction of music sociology in China and reflecting Chinese characteristics	

Source: A New Theory of Musicology by Yang Yandi (2011)

In short, music sociology, the intersection between sociology and musicology, has been introduced to China from overseas

It has only been more than a decade, and it is still a young major, which still needs to be explored and localized by researchers in many aspects. At present, there are very few research results on the integration of Chinese local literature. Using art songs become the main form of Chinese music, and become the main social phenomenon, the social facts, explore the background, the use of art songs to explore the association of music works and social phenomenon, and explore the association between art songs and national culture, to further enrich the Chinese music sociology research is of great significance.

Research on modern and contemporary ancient poetry and art songs

As a very heavy literature treasure in China, ancient poetry has a long history, and ancient poetry and ballads are the crystallization of vocal art, sung from generation to generation. Chinese modern and modern ancient poetry and music began with the May 4th New Culture Movement. Some Chinese intellectuals, such as

Huang Zi, who returned from Shanghai, took modern and modern ancient poetry as music, integrated their Western music, and created contemporary ancient poetry and art songs, with traditional Chinese characteristics. Zhao Jiping and other modern Chinese artists, It also uses verses from the Book of Songs to compose music and compose for it, Combining the traditional Chinese national style with the twelve Western tone techniques, Make a Chinese traditional music and a little more new music elements; The young Lord combined this aria with the narrative tone, Developed a unique means of writing, With the song Dynasty great poet Su Shi's famous patriotic poem "Nianujiao Red Cliff with the ancient" closely organically combined together, Write su Shi's poems in the kind of open-minded, rich and delicate, touching patriotic feelings, Formed the unique personality artistic style of this song; There is also a long poem, "Maple Bridge moored at night", As Mr.Li Yinghai has completed the creation by himself, A lyric from a poem called "Maple Bridge Park at Night" by Zhang Ji, a poet of the Tang Dynasty, The artistic conception of this poem. The topic that the author wants to study now is how to explore the profound connotation of modern and contemporary ancient poetry art songs from the aspects of broken words, singing skills and songs from the background material of a famous modern and contemporary Chinese classical musician as the modern and contemporary ancient poetry art songs.

Modern and contemporary ancient poetry art songs refers to the new song genre formed by the selection of Chinese classical poetry and their composition, or the appropriate music melody to make them combined into beautiful lyrics and music. When compiling and matching appropriate melodies of ancient poems, we should not only follow the beautiful melody, but also follow the original content of ancient poems and songs, and follow the thoughts and feelings that the lyricist wants to express. In this way, the original content of ancient poems and songs can be more accurately expressed, with more appropriate lyrics and melodies composed. Before the beginning of singing modern and contemporary ancient poetry art songs, we should be familiar with the writing background and the moral meaning of the poem, coupled with our own understanding of the connotation of the lyrics and music, and finally cooperate with the singer's skilled modern and contemporary ancient poetry art and song techniques, so as to express the connotation of modern and contemporary ancient poetry art and songs. In addition, the emergence and development process of modern and contemporary Chinese ancient poetry and art songs should also be deeply influenced by the "school music songs". Some of the early Chinese intellectuals, new intellectuals went abroad to study vocal music and received excellent western European music culture education. After returning to China, they composed music according to their own western composition techniques and passed them on in class, so they are known as "school music song".(1920s-1940 s) By the period of the New Culture Movement, it began to gradually use ancient Chinese poetry as songs, and used excellent western music composing techniques to compose music. The development of Chinese poetry and art cooperation reached its peak in this stage, songs as a novel and unique writing genre, in writing will begin to use the use of staff notation, and writing the piano accompaniment with the use of Musical Instruments, also timely and properly foil the emotional charm of art songs, for the new era of modern and contemporary poetry art development laid a solid foundation.

Since the beginning of the last century, under the condition of the further improvement of the social, economic and cultural level, and under the tide of the country's strong support for the development of various cultural undertakings, many composers have emerged to write songs according to ancient poems, innovated with their superb composing skills, and created some beautiful ancient poems and songs. Liao Shangguo, a famous music writer in China, composed music based on Su Shi's poem "Nianujiao Red Cliff" in the early 1920s, and thus produced the first ancient poem ballad of "the river goes east" in modern China. Since the seventy s our country modern and contemporary ancient poetry art songs gradually on the road of recovery, its development also makes a group of people clinging to the most ancient cultural heritage, a large number of scholars also began to compose a lot of ancient poems, ancient poetry music production and sung also began to gradually into the liberation of the feudal political thought. Since the 1980s and 1990s, the composer has combined the classical temperament of ancient Chinese poetry with the creation skills of western modern music. The author uses a lot of primitive folk language in his creation to express his rich emotions. A large number of beautiful works have emerged in the creation of ancient poems and songs. However, at the present stage, there are very few theoretical research materials to discuss art songs as independent research in music education. Therefore, the theoretical research results and available data on the research of modern and contemporary Chinese poetry can be said to be rare. After China's reform and opening up, the relevant research results of music sociology have increasingly surfaced.552 articles on modern and contemporary ancient poetry and art songs. It mainly involves the development of context, charm, singing style, creative characteristics and some singing skills of modern and contemporary Chinese ancient poetry art songs. Liu, for example, master's thesis "contemporary folk songs and' China 'love theme comparison", Qiu Yi "on the inheritance of modern lyrics to classical poetry style", wei wei's early and modern and contemporary folk studies, liu contemporary song lyrics reference, the relationship between contemporary song ci and classical poetry, ying-ying li tang and song song and li qun modern folk songs such as journals, liu "theory of modern pop songs in classical poetry inheritance and innovation", etc., these articles mostly from the perspective of literature to the study. And usually only one poet's work is selected for specific analysis.

Table 2: The number of literature articles of ancient Chinese poetry and art songs

Research on singing aesthetic innovation		Characteristic comparison of different singing versions	Literary study of ancient poetry and art songs		Development research in China	Research on the integration with Chinese opera	The analysis of the singing style	Characteristics of the specific repertoire analysis	Study on the creation and compilation of new singing of ancient poetry	Analysis of artistic characteristics
65	11			8	37	23	156	46	7	34

Source: collation of this study

As can be seen from Table 2, there are the most articles on the singing style of ancient poems and artistic songs, followed by the research on the aesthetic innovation of singing. The number of characteristic analysis from the perspective of literature is followed by the characteristic comparison of different singing versions and the creation and compilation of new singing of ancient poems. Above data analysis can be very clearly found in the ancient poetry art song research about repertoire characteristics of scholars are interested in, focusing on the practice of the number is considerable, from the theoretical perspective of ancient poetry art song history development, different repertoire study of the comparative research also by the attention of scholars. In addition, there are some crossover articles that do not directly analyze the music ontology of ancient poetry art songs, but discuss the innovation and inheritance of ancient poetry art songs. The following figure can give a clear overview of the current research situation of ancient poetry and art songs:

Figure 2: Research overview of classical poetry and art songs

Source: collation of this study

The "historical development research" in Figure 2 contains the development course of Chinese ancient poetry and art songs, which is a significant part of the theoretical research. The literary analysis section includes not only research from the perspective of pure literature, but also style research and artistic characteristics analysis that do not involve the research of music ontology. This division can make us clear that there are not many articles related to music analysis, so it is necessary to fill the gap in the musicology research of singing analysis.

Can be seen from the above academic achievements in the current study on modern and contemporary ancient poetry art songs presents a wide coverage difficult state, although from the perspective of music history of the development of the general context, also have from the details of music ontology analysis, but together has not yet formed modern and contemporary ancient poetry art songs thematic research results. If you narrow down the search again, Looking for the modern and contemporary ancient poetry and art songs from the perspective of music sociology, In the process of circulation, only huang Tengteng published in the journal "Modern and Contemporary Ancient poetry Art Songs in China in September 2002"; Exploring the innovation and development of traditional music with the consciousness of modern music, "On the innovation and evolution of Chinese Traditional Music" published in October 2016; To choose the music sociology culture range combing contemporary poetry art song development characteristics of only Cao if published in March 2019, the music culture perspective of modern and contemporary poetry art songs inheritance and wang focus

on music teaching direction published in April 2019, "modern and contemporary ancient poetry art songs music class promotion status quo and countermeasure analysis", In addition, Fu Han published the Theoretical Study on the Inheritance and Aesthetic Changes of Traditional Art Songs in February 2020 from the perspective of aesthetic changes in inheritance. The above preliminary analysis of the morphological characteristics of modern and contemporary ancient poetry art songs from the perspective of music sociology has some research highlights and the research accumulation of modern and contemporary ancient poetry art songs. Such as Huang Tengpeng in the paper chose several representative countries art songs, from the horizontal contrast to build the world art song form differences of the overall framework, the pioneering research the different political historical background of art songs from the soil to the form of cultural gene analysis, makes the different cultural background of art songs in the content with style differences. Yang Shuguang's article focuses on China's modern and contemporary ancient poetry and art songs, and objectively pays attention to the origin and penetration of Chinese culture in the atmosphere of the integration of Chinese and Western cultures, and finally forms the dissemination process and future development trend of modern and contemporary ancient poetry and art songs. Compared with the research depth of the inheritance and development of traditional culture, Cao Ruo first defined the scope and definition concept of modern and contemporary ancient poetry and art songs in the combing of the communication process, and considered the historical characteristics of its evolution and development as well as the path of publicity and promotion. And modern and contemporary ancient poetry art song research can provide information source for music education, wang Ji'an will try to network technology for modern and contemporary ancient poetry art song MOOC teaching promotion, put forward the ancient words art songs must follow the social trend, according to the needs of modern people adjust the mode of transmission.

Through the above analysis, it can be found that the music of the 20th-40th century is the focus of previous research. And less to the ancient poetry or modern and contemporary ancient poetry art songs alone as a special music style to carry out special research work. Moreover, the majority of musicology research discusses the form, while few studies focus on singing types. For example, more meaningful academic papers: Yue Li's Preliminary Study on the Evolution of Chinese Art and Music in the 20th Century, Wang Zhenya's "Youth Main Music Review", Zuo Xia's "Discussion on the Rhythm Characteristics of Traditional Chinese Literary Music" and so on. They are all theoretical summaries of the evolution of ancient Chinese music, as well as the individual types or schools of ancient Chinese poetry. However, the research data on the artistic characteristics of modern and contemporary ancient poetry art songs in the 20-40 years of the 20th century are relatively lacking, especially for the research on the aesthetic characteristics and singing styles of modern and contemporary ancient poetry art songs in all stages of the 20-40 years, the available materials are particularly lacking.

For these factors, This paper makes a new integration from the research ideas and content, Taking the development course and theme content sorting of modern and contemporary ancient poetry and art songs as the main line, Deep into the level of artistic and cultural development related to social development, In order to present the characteristics of the inheritance and development of modern and contemporary ancient poetry and art songs from a real sociological perspective, The author has collected the research data related to the ancient poems and songs through various channels, In view of the influence of rational factors such as the genre, theme, melody, style, tonality and steel companion of the work, And the emotional impact of the creation of art to be carefully analyzed; It realizes the realistic analysis of modern and contemporary Chinese ancient poetry and art songs in the perspective of music sociology. In short, in this paper, because of the sociology and music is too close, need the development of modern and contemporary ancient poetry art song history list, but more on the basis of historical analysis of the music culture factors of social reasons, form a persuasive modern and contemporary ancient poetry art song style inductive results. On the contrary, if there is no horizontal research system on the history of modern and contemporary Chinese poetry, art and songs under the background of music sociology, then the research content is only limited to the simplicity and regularity of the style of modern and contemporary ancient poetry and art songs. Therefore, my doctoral thesis strives to conduct in-depth research on the classical modern and contemporary ancient poetry and art songs, which began with the development process of modern and contemporary ancient poetry and art songs in modern and contemporary China. Gradually deep into the artistic characteristics of representative works in various periods, and finally into the connotation analysis of lyrics, the analysis of singing skills, and the treatment of singing emotion, so as to make the research more academic valuable.

Important Concept definition

Music management (music sociology): it is a new professional category that integrates management science and musicology. It takes various sound problems and forms controlled by human beings as the important objects, and focuses on exploring the interrelated society between human beings and sound, which is generally known as sound management science. Music sociology will song behavior (including various song behavior) as a social problem, using different means in the field, discusses the art and social activities of various aspects of each other, trying to find out the relationship between art problems and social phenomenon and its

change rule, and to evaluate it and to predict the change of some related phenomena, and its summary, summarized as the whole concept.

Irrationality (sensitivity): relative to rationality, it is the most intuitive way to feel, know and express things. The perceptual factors in music research are the same as the perceptual understanding in life. Its sensitivity is mainly reflected in the basic premise of music rationality. It is the opposite of music rationality, the element of the rational rationalization of music, and the key principle and objective conditions of the unity of sensitivity and rationality.

Reason: Reason is rational knowledge, which refers to the ideological forms or activities of concepts, judgments, inferences, etc. Reason is relative to human emotion, its essence is negation and doubt, do not rely on intuition and senses, do it can think according to the basic law of the development of things and the principle of self-evolution, have a comprehensive understanding of analysis, summary and reasonable solutions, etc. In the field of musicology research, rationality usually refers to the ability to summarize the concept of people's thinking, and to make judgment, classification, synthesis, comparison, and inference.

Music form elements: "Music form" refers to the overall characteristics of the noumenon of music in a specific historical period. The musical form elements based on the perspective of music sociology refer to the collective musical aesthetic concept expressed under a special historical stage, and have the special form characteristics distinguished from others for a certain musical matter.

Music culture style: Music culture includes the real and concrete social existence form of music, and the overall style formed on this inherent form is the external expression form of music culture appearance. From the perspective of connotation, the music cultural style is real and concrete. From the perspective of external characteristics, music cultural style is through the high-level cognition of the whole music in social and historical events.

Music audience: In short, "who the music needs to be done for". "Audience" is a professional term in communication, meaning the person who receives social information. The music audience has made a clear definition of the group receiving information, that is, the group object of the information received after the dissemination of music works, which plays a decisive role in judging the effect of music communication.

Conclusion

Through the all-round study and reading of modern and contemporary Chinese ancient poetry and art songs, we pay attention to the development of modern and contemporary ancient poetry and art songs, so as to understand the inheritance and new changes of modern and contemporary Chinese ancient poetry and art songs. It is beneficial to understand the inheritance and development of modern music schools from a overall perspective, or the interpretation of ancient culture. This article will also refer to China's articles and related library resources, by obtaining relevant Chinese poetry reading and modern and contemporary poetry art songs playing video, this data summary and classification, thus system to master the subject research trend and development, and indirectly obtain the current academic research results, summarize and compare other scholars research deficiencies, clear research trend and research content. The author's research problem is the study of modern and contemporary ancient poetry, art and song from the perspective of music sociology, so the theoretical basis is first the relevant content of music sociology. Max weber, in 1921, wrote the world's first music education sociology study of the foundation of music education, but because the book on knowledge contains the law, acoustics and mathematical knowledge, so for the general readers and music art researchers, have a lot of difficulty. Max Webb's *Philosophy of Music Education and EuroCentrism* is a translation of Sun Honglei (2022). For this detailed analysis and discussion, he pointed out that Weber's philosophy of music education has created a new vision for people to study the formal elements of music education, the cultural style of music education and the evolution process of music education. As the preface to the English translation concludes: Weber found the tension between the basic principles of rhythm and harmony (the latter tends to be philosophical rational and the former to be irrational). The Soviet music theorist Sohalkin made a unique and comprehensive discussion on the scope of discussion, ideological history and other related issues of music sociology. This book rigorously explains the complicated concept of "music culture" in the world, from every cell of human society and culture development to every existing relationship, from the perspective of "music culture" and every possibility of history. And "music perception" as the central topic of sound sociology research, through applied psychology, statistics and other means. Thus on the development of sound society and the common development of human community (the collection of the public). Sohar (A. Sochor) First of all, the main object of the theoretical research of music sociology is "human society and Musical instrument life", that is, the social process in which the actual function of music culture occurs under specific historical conditions.

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